

Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI)

Use of OneNote as an ELN in undergraduate teaching labs at the University of Southampton in the department of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering Case Study
PSDI Report

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Report Date: 23rd January 2026

Publishing Information

Use of OneNote as an ELN in undergraduate teaching labs at the University of Southampton in the department of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering Case Study

PSDI-Case-Study-Series:Report_3

Report Date: 23rd January 2026

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18256918

Published by University of Southampton

Funding Information

Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure

PSDI acknowledges the funding support by the EPSRC grants EP/X032701/1, EP/X032663/1 and EP/W032252/1

Title: *Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure Phase 1b EP/X032701/1*

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Project Details

Project Name	Use of OneNote as an ELN in undergraduate teaching labs at the University of Southampton in the department of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering Case Study
Project Dates	01/10/2024-30/06/2025
Website	PSDI Website

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Project Description

This case study was undertaken to investigate the process of implementing OneNote in the Undergraduate Chemistry Labs at the University of Southampton.

Project Data & Materials

Both data and guidance have been made available for this case study:

- Guidance on [Using Microsoft OneNote as an Electronic Lab Notebook](#) has been made available via the PSDI Knowledgebase.
- The raw data from the survey that was completed by the students at the end of the trial period, and the associated survey questions have both been uploaded to the Zenodo Record alongside this report, under the file names [Raw_Survey_Results_OneNote_CaseStudy.xlsx](#) and [Raw_Survey_Questions_OneNote_CaseStudy.pdf](#).

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1 Introduction

In late 2019, the undergraduate teaching laboratories in Chemistry and Chemical Engineering at the University of Southampton (UoS) underwent a major refurbishment, including the introduction of teaching laptops to the labs. This paved the way for the teaching labs to phase out physical notebooks. Yet this phasing out process was not without its complications, and it was not until 2024 a comprehensive replacement for the old physical notebooks was fully implemented.

In this case study, we will look at the background for the implementation of an Electronic Laboratory Notebook (ELN) for undergraduate students. We will discuss why we chose OneNote, how we implemented OneNote as an ELN, and discuss the positives and negatives of the implementation with suggestions for readers on about how to approach a similar implementation.

2 The Background

As part of the refurbishment of the department of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering level 4 and 5 teaching laboratories at the University of Southampton in April 2019, a LapSafe system for teaching laptops was installed. The LapSafe system provides a storage and charging solution for laptops where users can check out a laptop for individual use within the laboratory. Providing these laptops enabled students to more easily access proprietary software in the lab (such as dedicated software for NMR and Mass Spectroscopy machines) whilst minimising the health and safety risks associated with students bringing their own laptops into the laboratories.

The introduction of the LapSafe system to the teaching laboratories, enabled a conversation about the teaching process going paperless to begin, followed by a plan (as part of a curriculum review) to phase out the use of physical note books as part of the teaching process. Shortly after this plan was put into practice, the global COVID19 pandemic occurred and brought with it wide scale lockdowns. Lecturers were suddenly faced with the difficulties of teaching lab-based chemistry remotely, which posed a whole new set of challenges, some of which did not disappear following the return to normality after the pandemic. Given the complexity and time commitment required to implement new digital tools, developing a digital notebook during the pandemic and the subsequent years was not deemed a practical use of the very limited time available to teaching staff.

In 2025, members of the Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI) team started discussions with the teaching staff at the University of Southampton to understand what facilities and software were present in the labs at the university. The PSDI team had an interest in the use of ELNs within chemistry stemming from previous research and pilot activities conducted with other universities in the United Kingdom. This discussion led to a collaboration between PSDI and the University of Southampton teaching team to implement a comprehensive digital note-taking system using [Microsoft OneNote](#) for undergraduates. OneNote is a digital notebook that enables users to capture notes in a variety of ways and across a variety of devices.

Student experience of effective note-taking and the use of digital tools is vital. Learning how to correctly record experiments is a fundamental skill in any lab-based science. As laboratories across academia and industry move from paper to digital record-keeping, students need to develop strong digital note-taking skills. Incorporating tools such as OneNote and ELNs into teaching ensures that students acquire these essential skills for both their academic progression and their future professional roles.

2.1 The Students

In this case study, the students introduced to the OneNote ELN were first-year undergraduates who were new to university study. The implementation took place during the first semester of the 2024 academic year, when OneNote was introduced as an ELN for the first time. First year students have 6 hours of practical laboratory work every week in the first semester. By introducing this new notebook at the beginning of their university careers, the teaching staff are able to ensure that the new students have a strong foundation for their future laboratory work, and are not trying to change the practices of students later in their careers who may be more resistant to change. The selected cohort of students, and their use of OneNote as an ELN, provides the basis for the data and suggestions that we present in this paper.

2.2 Environmental factors

A tangential benefit to introducing a digital note-taking solution at the University of Southampton (regardless of the platform) was that it fits within the scope of improving the grade of the [LEAF Certification](#) for the undergraduate teaching labs. LEAF Certification aims to improve the sustainability and efficiency of laboratories. By phasing out paper lab notebooks and replacing them with digital note-taking capabilities, the teaching laboratories can reduce the physical waste that they produce. It is important to note that there is still an environmental cost to using computers, and students need to be aware that computers and compute are not "free" resources to a university, even if they are free at point of use.

2.3 OneNote

There are a great variety of digital note-taking tools available to researchers and students. Examples of digital note-taking tools include:

- Basic text editors such as Notepad for WindowsOS or TextEdit on MacOS
- Generic note-taking tools such as OneNote, Obsidian or Notion, that provide additional functionality
- Off the shelf Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELNs) designed for use in laboratory environments and often with discipline-specific functionality, for example Revvity Signals and Dotmatics LabArchives ¹
- Bespoke ELNs are typically developed in-house for a specific user group or scientific domain. Bespoke ELNs can also include heavily modified off the shelf offerings, designed for very specific laboratory environments.

Choosing a specific ELN (simple or complex) can be a difficult process if you are starting from scratch. In this case study we present our process and the decisions made at the University of Southampton for the undergraduate teaching laboratories and is not intended to help a reader to select a different ELN for their needs. If you are looking for guidance on the wider considerations around selecting a suitable ELN, we recommend taking a look at the guidance and related links provided on the PSDI Knowledge Base about [choosing an ELN](#).

¹This list of ELNs is not comprehensive. A more complete list can be found at [ELN Finder](#) however, a reader must be aware that the offerings on the market are changing rapidly and ELN finder may not reflect the latest changes in the market.

2.3.1 Reasons why OneNote met our requirements

We chose to use OneNote as an ELN for the first year undergraduate students primarily because it was a tool that teaching staff were already recommending that students should use for other work. No additional tools were investigated as alternatives, and therefore we will not be presenting a comparison of how OneNote might be better or worse as an ELN for undergraduate students. There are, however, a number of reasons why OneNote is suitable for use as an ELN for students:

Cost: The University of Southampton (at the time of publication) has adopted Microsoft Office 365 as its preferred software platform. OneNote is one of the tools that come as part of Office 365, meaning that the department was not required to pay additional costs to use the software. In comparison, choosing a dedicated ELN tool can be expensive. For example, from our examples above, Revvity charges up over \$1000 per per year per user and Dotmatics charges around \$500 per year per user (*numbers drawn from publicly available webpages at the time of writing*). This cost may be out of reach for many academic institutions.

Simplicity: OneNote has a limited set of functionality that are sufficient for the requirements of first year student laboratory classes, and although the software has quirks (discussed in section 4.2) it is relatively easy to use making it easy to learn and adopt for both staff and students.

Integration with Blackboard: The University of Southampton uses Blackboard (and the Blackboard Ultra UI) as a virtual learning environment for its students. The platform enables teaching staff to upload and disseminate teaching materials such as lecture slides, laboratory practical scripts, health and safety information, and videos. Microsoft provides [Learning Tool Integration \(LTI\)](#) that enables Microsoft products including OneNote and Microsoft Teams to be linked and integrated directly into Blackboard. This integration enables staff to configure a OneNote notebook for a class. This is discussed in greater detail in section 3.1.

A Teaching Tool: A OneNote notebook is effectively a blank canvas enabling staff to set it up in a multitude of ways. This makes it an ideal tool for building a teaching platform. We found it was simple to replicate the layout of a traditional physical lab notebook in a digital format to provide a template for students to use. It was also possible to create pages of supporting and supplemental information for the students to access and take content from if required. The layout and content are clear for the students making it easy for them to interact with the notebook and without any risk of them being overloaded with difficult to use functionality or complex features that are not relevant for their classes.

Although not a complete list of the reasons that OneNote can be used as a teaching notebook, the four sections above provide some of the key reasons as to why OneNote would meet our requirements in the teaching laboratories.

3 Implementation of a OneNote ELN

The implementation can be divided into four main themes: Hardware, Systems, Content, and Training. Hardware covers the physical hardware used in the laboratory; Systems considers how OneNote interacts with other software in the learning environment; Content focuses on the work that was required to set up the OneNote notebook for use ; and Training covers the training that was delivered to the students before and during the course.

3.1 Hardware

Of the setup elements in this project, the hardware element was the simplest part of the implementation because the University teaching laboratories already have good hardware facilities in place thanks to a refurbishment in 2019. Each of the lab desks has power outlets and both laboratories have complete WiFi cover (no wired connections). As part of the refurbishment, the university invested in a LapSafe system enabling students to checkout a laptop for personal use during laboratory sessions with enough laptops for one per student. The system has a twofold benefit:

- **Ease of Use:** All students have access to the same equipment running the same operating system (Windows 10 OS at the time of the study). This means there are no problems with students forgetting to bring their own laptops with them or any operating system incompatibilities with the OneNote software.
- **Safety:** During the chemistry classes, the students use a multitude of chemicals leading to potential contamination of any laptops brought into the laboratory. For health and safety reasons, it is important that these laptops are not removed from the laboratory into public and private spaces such as lecture theatres and homes.

Because the hardware already existed, no additional steps were required for this section of the implementation.

3.2 Systems

The software configuration was more complex. It was necessary to set up a Class Notebook, a specific type of OneNote notebook, for a specific teaching module in order to enable a teacher/student relationship to be created.² This required a Team for the class to be configured within Microsoft Teams where the information about teacher and student roles, and the members of the module are added to provide access to the OneNote notebook embedded within it. The Blackboard virtual learning environment provides support for the administration of users allowing teaching staff to associate a Teams instance with a module with just a few clicks, and thus removing the burden of manually adding students and other staff to Teams and OneNote. An added bonus is that the lecturers did not have to actively keep track of students (for this purpose) who changed enrolment status for the module because this is done natively through Blackboard, which updates the list of OneNote users twice daily. ***Note:** When a module is not yet active or visible to students, we observed warnings displayed on the Blackboard interface that initially caused confusion about the access and status of the linked OneNote notebook. Despite the warnings, there were no actual problems with the notebook and the warnings were no longer displayed when the module was made accessible to students.*

Once Blackboard has been used to set up a Microsoft Teams site associated with the correct teaching module, the set up of the notebook can begin. During creation of the Microsoft Teams set up, you are invited to create a Class OneNote associated with that Teams site. A Class Notebook is a specific type of OneNote notebook that allows for a teacher/student tier system to work, for in depth information please refer to the [Microsoft documentation](#). During the set up of the class notebook, there are a number of decisions that need to be made. For example, which individual pages will students have access to, what will the shared library of pages look like, what collaborative pages you want to include, and which pages you want to have in your teachers only area (an excellent place to store pages that will be published to students later or

²At the University of Southampton a Module is a block of connected teaching materials that confers a certain number of the credits to the required number of credits for a student to pass a year. Typically, a student will have 8 modules over a teaching year, 4 in the first semester and 4 in the second

working pages that are still in the draft stage). Each Class Notebook has a teacher's only area and a section for each of the students in that module. Within the student section each student has a section that only they or the teachers, but not other students can see. It is possible to set-up a collaborative area of the notebook that multiple students can work within (such as for group project work), but we choose not to use that functionality within our implementation.

If you have previously set up a OneNote notebook, you can choose to copy in elements from the existing notebook (such as a module from a previous semester) reducing duplication and saving time. It is also possible to copy and paste from pages in other notebooks if it is not possible to directly import them. Pages from private notebooks can also be added during the import stages, allowing content to be developed in a private notebook before being used to populate a teaching notebook. **Note:** *Our experience indicates that it is important to perform the setup (discussed in more depth later) within the OneNote built-in to Teams rather than another version of the software.*

3.3 Content

OneNote can be used as an infinitely sized empty notebook, but an empty notebook does not make an effective teaching tool. For first year undergraduates with limited experience of capturing notes about their experiments, it helpful to provide a notebook page with a predefined structure or template to help guide the students in what to record. We also strongly recommend including a 'Help' page for the students that contains useful tricks and tips to improve their experience with OneNote and to answer common questions. Below are suggestions for pages to include based on our experiences at the University of Southampton.

- The Template Lab Page:

- We created a simple page with 6 or 7 headings for sections appropriate for students to include in the notes for their experiments. These are the headings that we chose to include for the template page:
 - * Experiment Identifier, Date and Experiment Name
 - * Experiment/ Reaction Aim
 - * Experiment Overview/Reaction Scheme
 - * Chemical Quantities and Hazards
 - * Observations
 - * Findings
 - * Conclusions

These headings aligned with the information teaching staff expected students to record during their experiments and with the criteria used in their assessment. Each heading also had two or three prompting questions as subheadings to help the students understand what was expected of them.

- An important addition to the template page is a line of hyphens (–) 95 characters long. OneNote has an unlimited page size, which is unhelpful if you want to print or print to PDF your notebook page. The line of hyphens gives the students a visible indicator of whether their writing is extending outside an A4 page. **Note:** *The 95 characters does not take into account printing margins, which may cause issues with printing if students are writing right up to the edge.*

- The Help Pages:

- The first help page provided was a 'useful tools' page. This page includes examples of chemical compound tables, how to use the in-built symbol and equation tools, how

to insert Excel sheets, and suggestions for chemical drawing software that could be used to draw reactions (including how to import images from them).

- The second help page provided information about the layout of a notebook page. It explained the 95 hyphens (and provided a spare copy of the hyphens), different viewing options for the notebook page, how to set up the page (such as infinite size page, single A4 and format as lined pages), and how to rotate images. OneNote does not allow users to freely rotate images, but instructions on how to rotate images was added after students requested guidance on how to rotate images so that larger NMR Spectra images could be added within the A4 width of the page.

The template notebook and help pages were grouped under a section called Empty Notebooks within the Class Notebook shared library of pages. Students were able to copy the template notebook and help pages into their own private sections of the Class Notebook. The aim is to get the students to think about what they are bringing into their notebooks rather than having everything pre-populated for them.

3.4 Training

The final element in successfully implementing OneNote (or any core piece of software) is to provide the users with adequate training. In this instance, the training had two components: first, teaching students to use the OneNote software; and second, demonstrating what effective laboratory note-taking looks like, regardless of platform.

At the University of Southampton, first year students are split into 4 groups and are given laboratory introductions in these groups. We utilised the introductory lecture (3h in length) in the laboratory as an opportunity to:

- ask students to access the OneNote software and Class Notebook through Blackboard to get it to sync with the OneNote app on their laptops.
- show the students where the help pages within the Class Notebook are located.
- get the students to copy an empty notebook template page into their private areas within the notebook so they could work on it.
- ask the students to complete the template notebook page for a 'mock mental experiment' of 'making a cup of tea'. This allowed the students to fill out the template and start to understand what the different sections would be used for.

Although the training we provided was a good start, we discuss in later (section 4.3) that a longer training period would have benefitted the students. Regular check-ins with students during the initial weeks and months would also have allowed us to provide additional support during an intensive learning period.

4 Outcomes

In this section, we discuss what went well with the configuration and implementation of OneNote as an ELN for teaching. We will also describe some of the issues that we encountered. The focus of this section is on the technical side of the implementation, but also draws on the student experience where relevant.

4.1 Positive

Overall, the implementation of OneNote as an ELN in the teaching labs at the University of Southampton went well (with a small number of issues, laid out in the following section). The student response to OneNote was broadly positive, with the main features they enjoyed being the ability to access their notes anywhere and the auto save feature (Figure 1). So long as the students have access to an internet connection, they could access their notes from anywhere. With a physical notebook it would have to be carried everywhere to facilitate this and bring with it the challenges of contamination of chemicals outside the lab as discussed earlier. We view it as positive that the students recognise this key benefit of digital note-taking.

Figure 1: Favourite features of OneNote as a digital laboratory note taking tool

Another key positive identified by the students was the way that the digital notebook helps them to organise their work. Within the digital notebook the template creates an automatic structure reminding the students what to record, and it is also possible to copy and paste elements to move content around. A physical notebook does not provide easy alternative ways to organise the notes in this way.

Another benefit of OneNote that led to a positive experience for the teaching staff included the integration of Teams and OneNote with Blackboard and Blackboard Ultra. This integration handles administrative tasks, such as keeping student lists up to date, that would otherwise need to be done manually. This reduces the workload for staff members. This project would have been less successful (or even a failure) if the staff needed to spend more time performing administrative tasks than delivering teaching and support to the students. The fact that the laboratories already had laptops made the setup and roll out very easy for a number of reasons:

- The provision of laptops that did not need to leave the laboratory was an advantage for health and safety, preventing devices that may have been contaminated ending up in places where the students eat and sleep.

- All the hardware was provided, allowing all students to participate regardless of their financial background.
- Both the hardware and software are managed by the University of Southampton IT department. Because all the laptops in the laboratories are the same, with the same specifications and software, students should not encounter issues with software versions or not having hardware capable of running the required software. **Note:** *However, we did find there were cases where different laptops did behave differently*

Part of the goal of this project was to provide a teaching tool. In any practical scientific field making good records of experiments is a fundamental skill. Although some departments provide specific training or a handbook on note-taking, having a template within the notebook is an effective way to provide best practice guidance for the students whilst still allowing flexibility. Benefits include:

- Providing a structured outline to prompt the student to gather information in all the relevant areas
- Allowing the student to reflect on how the structure should be modified for an individual experiment and how this can be applied to future research experiments
- Allowing past work to be more easily revisited as the entries are of a similar structure
- Setting up the template also allowed students to work within an A4 page width limit if they chose to. Although the option was not enforced, by keeping text entered into the notebook within the confines of an A4 page, if the notepad page is printed (as a hard copy or to PDF) it allows for students to directly submit their notebook page for marking.
- Clarity of notes.
 - Handwriting and spelling skill varies across individuals. OneNote allows students to type their notes. The benefit of having typed notes is that they are easier to read for both students and teaching staff. However, note-taking on computer does not solve the problem of poor note-taking, and it is therefore important that students are encouraged to capture complete notes.
 - Tables are very easy to put together on a computer, enabling tables of chemicals, balances, and hazards to be easily made. On paper students would need to bring rulers and other such drawing equipment to the lab. A table created on a computer is likely to be clear and neat in a way that a hand drawn table may not be.
 - Chemical structural representation can be added through software such as Chem-Draw. Digital versions of representations are clearer and likely to be more accurate than hand drawn equivalents. This assumption is supported by the majority of students surveyed, Figure 2) .
- The ability to add data from other sources to OneNote is a key advantage over paper. Manually adding tables of data or graphs to paper notebooks increases the likelihood of transcription errors. Print outs of data, diagrams, or charts require a printer and glue or tape to affix data into a traditional notebook, and the attached sheet can subsequently fall out and get lost. Data that can be digitally added to OneNote include:
 - Photos of experimental set ups, allowing students to recreate the experiment in future if required

- Images downloaded from the internet, for example, equipment, hazard information, chemical structures. This supplemental information for the experiment can be useful for increased comprehension of the work either at the time of the experiment or in the future. It is important to ensure that images and other content are correctly referenced, and this is another important skill for the students to learn.
- Output from laboratory equipment, such as NMR spectra and key data related to the experiment, that historically would have been printed out and stuck in
- Files such as Excel, PDF or Word documents can be added to the notebook, creating a direct link to data that has been collected and analysed during an experiment all in one place. OneNote is able to display the information directly from a number of sources.

Figure 2: Students were asked how they added chemical structures or notation to their OneNote note books

4.2 Negative

Although the overall experience with OneNote as a notebook for teaching was positive, OneNote does not provide all the capabilities that would be desirable in an ELN for teaching students. We will cover the key ones here:

- The equation editor in OneNote is the same as that provided in Word. This interface is not simple to use and although there are shortcuts available, it is an area where paper notebooks have an advantage. OneNote does have drawing input as an option, as well as a writing to text option that could be used to improve the writing of equations within OneNote if the hardware supported good drawing input (such as with a stylus on a touchscreen laptop). **Note:** *The laptops that the University of Southampton use in the lab are touchscreen, which does facilitate digital writing with a stylus. The laptops were originally provided to the university with styluses. However, the styluses are no longer given out to students because they often get lost, taken away or rendered unusable by chemical damage. One solution that has been proposed is to provide students with a stylus along with lab coat and lab specs at the beginning of first year, with replacements needing to be paid for by students to prevent them going missing.*
- As a generic note-taking piece of software OneNote has no in-built chemical structure representation tools. This means that if students want or are required to add structures

to their work they have to use an external piece of software such as ChemDraw to add them. The University of Southampton holds a license for ChemDraw and it is the tool preferred by staff for the students to use. More institutions using OneNote as a teaching tool in labs may provide an incentive for the development of a community plug-in to provide additional chemical functionality to OneNote.

- A downside that caused repeated issues over the course of the term was that OneNote can be accessed in a number of ways, with each leading to a slightly different version of the software (even on the same operating system, this is not a WindowsOS vs MacOS issue). The main routes for access are:
 - Through the Microsoft teams app
 - Through the OneNote desktop app
 - Via the OneNote web browser interface
 - The OneNote phone app for Android and iOS. The different operating systems are not the cause of the problems, as discussed in more detail in section 4.3)

Each of these different versions has slightly different functionalities, both for the teaching staff and students. For example, the Microsoft equation editor is not available in the web version of OneNote. Also teaching staff are only able to delete sections from the Class Notebook on the web version, but not the other versions of OneNote.

Although the differences in functionality could be frustrating, other than a slight amount of time lost, these differences did not cause further problems. The main issues caused by the version differences was in sync quality between the different versions. Over the course of the module we had on more than one occasion an incident where students had used the web version of OneNote and due to sync issues, a total loss of data occurred for a given practical session. This problem occurred despite clearly instructing students at the beginning of the year to use the desktop version of OneNote, because it provided the greatest functionality for them.

However, when students access OneNote via the link in Blackboard, the web version is automatically opened. A number of students continued to navigate to OneNote this way rather than using the desktop app on the laptops, resulting in the data loss issues. Other than reiterating the use of the desktop version as the preferred version, no clear way of getting students to use a specific version of OneNote was identified. This issue is something that it is worth being aware of there is a plan to use OneNote through Blackboard, as the temptation to open OneNote through Teams or the web will be high as it is perceived by the students as being easier to access this way than through the desktop version, especially when they first start using the software). **Note:** *This was an issue at the time of writing, and may not be an issue in the future or in a different institution with a different internet/hardware setup.*

4.2.1 Student Feedback

The students provided feedback on what they would want to see improved or added with the use of OneNote as a teaching ELN, the results from the end of module survey can be seen in Figure 3 (23 of the 55 students answered with "Nothing Missing", these results have not been included in the figure).

Figure 3: Students were asked what they believed was missing from OneNote that would improve the experience

Some of the issues the students raised have already been mentioned in greater detail earlier in this section, but other issues identified include:

- Exporting to another file type, specifically PDF or Microsoft Word. Printing to PDF is possible in OneNote, and we cover why this issue arose and a potential fix in Section 4.3 as this is not a direct failure of the software.
- A number of critiques relating to "formatting", an issue that is difficult to fix in OneNote. OneNote has a more stripped back formatting suite of tools for writing and image placement compared with Word which is also available for students to use on the laptops. This reduced functionality does makes it more difficult to place and align text and images in OneNote, which can cause frustration for the students familiar with the capabilities of Word.
- The use of OneNote as an ELN. In the final survey and during conversations, a small number of students asked if we should be using different software or requesting to use their own note-taking software. The Obsidian note-taking software was mentioned on several occasions. Explanations for these requests included enhanced functionality available in different software, for example, integrated \LaTeX for easier equations or personal preference for other software. Because of the set-up of the classes for the first year undergraduates and the laptops in the laboratories, in particular the integration with Blackboard, it was necessary for the students to use OneNote rather than other tools that might have been personally preferred. At later stages in their learning when they have developed best practices around note-taking it might be more appropriate to allow them to use different tools. For different institutions with different ecosystems the pros and cons of OneNote can be weighed against the functionality of other note-taking software. There are advantages, as previously described, of ensuring consistency of software for large groups of students. The disadvantages of allowing students to use their tool of choice is a huge increase in

the overhead of managing the software, training, and troubleshooting of multiple note-taking tools.

4.3 Recommendations

This section describes the modifications that we would make to our OneNote set-up to improve the experience for both staff and students, but that are not inherently positive or negative.

- Although the initial training with the students went well, more follow up training and support through help sessions built into the teaching module would have aided the students and more importantly prevented and reduced some of the niggles felt earlier on. We believe that the following benefits would have been gained by additional training:
 - Students would have been able to give us faster feedback as well as showing us what they needed changing sooner. We did do mid-module feedback, but some of this came a little late into the module to usefully disseminate to all students.
 - A number of issues raised over the course of the module were around the functionality of OneNote (such as not being able to rotate images and being able to export to PDF) and in most cases these were functionalities available in OneNote, but that the students did not know how to use. Providing drop in sessions during the term would have helped deal with these issues faster
 - In hindsight, providing the training for a new piece of software in the first class of the year was not sufficient. Students struggled to remember all the information delivered during that session. If we had provided more training throughout the first couple of weeks of the term we could have easily answered more questions, guided students faster, and reinforced key concepts that were probably missed in the first couple of hours of teaching.
- How students interacted with the laptops in the lab. In the University of Southampton teaching laboratories, all the desks have laptop stands built in. They are designed to keep laptops off the work benches and position them at a better angle for viewing and typing. We observed that the stands were barely used during practicals. Students would use them if they were already in the correct position for them (height, location relative to that day's experiment) but were not inclined to move them if they were not already in the correct position. This is likely because laptop stands are stiff and difficult to move, making it hard for the students to quickly and easily adjust them. According to the teaching staff, the only times they get moved is when an experiment takes up enough space on the desk that students need to put the laptop out of the way so that they can conduct the experiment. This situation is worth bearing in mind if you are planning on setting up your own lab with laptops. Consider how the students are going to interact with the hardware and whether it is easy to use within the lab environment itself. Putting physical barriers in the way can prevent uptake or optimal use of the technology.
- OneNote is available in app form for both Android and iOS operating systems. Using the app version enables students to take photos and add them direct to a notebook page. This functionality provides an advantage over the paper notebooks, enabling pictures of the laboratory set-ups and equipment to be included within the notebook. These photos can then be annotated and used as a reference for future work. There are, however, some drawbacks to consider:
 - The ability to add photographs requires that the students own the appropriate hardware such as a mobile phone or tablet with a camera to do so. It is not guaranteed that all students have access to mobile devices that are capable of running OneNote

and no student should have their learning disadvantaged by their ability to afford technology.

- There are also challenges around health and safety. As already stated in 4.1, an advantage of the lab-only laptops is the prevention of contaminated hardware leaving the laboratory. At the University of Southampton, mobiles phones are not allowed to be used in the laboratory environment for health and safety reasons, to avoid contaminated equipment leaving the lab and also to remove distractions when handling chemicals. A shared device for capturing images could be an option to enable students to benefit from the ability to add photographs, but consideration would need to be given to how to manage transfer of images to the notebook pages and access. Images could for example be uploaded to a server location, from where the students could import the image into their own pages.

4.3.1 Student Feedback

Figure 4: Students reasons why they would return to paper note taking

At the end of the module, when we surveyed the students, we asked them if they would return to paper note-taking and why. Of the 55 students, 30 of them said they would consider retuning to paper. There are three primary reasons why students would choose to user paper notebooks rather than OneNote (presented in Figure 4):

- **Mathematical notation.** As previously described in Section 4.2, OneNote has limited functionality for adding mathematical notation and equations. This means that although some basic equations and trigonometry functions are supported, it is often easier for students to add more complex notation and equations in a paper notebook.
- **Knowledge retention and revision.** Students highlighted that sometimes they found that their retention of information was better when they used physical notebooks to write in rather than typing their notes into OneNote. This observation was also linked to how easy the students considered it to be to revise from digital notes. From a teaching perspective, it is worth considering the effectiveness of capturing notes digitally and whether suitable mitigations are possible.
- **Potential failure of the technology.** Some students were concerned about their data becoming lost, their ability to work in locations without an internet connection without a local copy of their work, or if they wanted to work somewhere without taking their laptops. It is important to consider issues of data security, backups, and contingencies for poor signal or loss of network connection within the laboratory or other places where the students may want to work. It is recommended to have a plan to manage technical problems that cause students to be unable to access their work or the software at critical times, such as during the laboratory or before assessments.

5 Conclusions

The thoughts and comments above are related to our specific example of using OneNote as a teaching Electronic Lab Notebook and may not be the experiences of others in the wider academic community. However, we hope that this document sparks conversation and is useful to those who are already in the process of implementing OneNote into the labs or are considering doing so. For many institutions OneNote is already available as part of a site wide license of Office 365, making it a cost effective way to introduce digital note-taking to students in laboratories.

We recommend the following resources for those interested in setting up ELNs: [Digital and electronic lab notebooks](#), including pages on [How to choose an ELN](#) and [Broader thoughts on using OneNote as ELN](#). If you are more interested in a domain specific ELN use [ELN Finder](#) to explore current options.

6 Acknowledgements

The authors would like to acknowledge the University of Southampton, School of Chemistry & Chemical Engineering Team: Professor Paul Duckmanton, Dr Thomas Logothetis, and Dr Samuel Perry for letting us run this study in their Undergraduate labs, and all of the students who contributed to our survey.